

OPTIMIZED YOLOV5 FOR SOLAR CELL SURFACE DEFECT DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

A solar cell defect detection method with an improved YOLO v5 algorithm is proposed for the characteristics of the complex solar cell image background, variable defect morphology, and large-scale differences. First, the deformable convolution is incorporated into the CSP module to achieve an adaptive learning scale and perceptual field size; then, the feature extraction capability of the model is enhanced by introducing the ECA-Net attention mechanism; finally, the model network structure is improved and one tiny defect prediction head is added to improve the accuracy of target detection at different scales. To further optimize and improve the YOLO v5 algorithm, this paper uses Mosaic and MixUp fusion data enhancement, K-meansCC clustering anchor box algorithm, and CIOU loss function to enhance the model performance. The experimental results show that the improved YOLO v5 algorithm achieves 89.64% mAP for the model trained on the solar cell EL image dataset, which is 7.85% higher than the mAP of the original algorithm, and the speed reaches 36.24 FPS, which can complete the solar cell defect detection task more accurately while meeting the real-time requirements.

In propose work we have modified YoloV5 but not experimented with advance YOLO family other version as like Yolo6, 7 or 8. So as extension we have trained same dataset with Yolov6 and its giving better prediction accuracy compare to Optimized YOLOv5.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the present stage, under the dual pressure of environmental pollution and the increasingly prominent traditional energy crisis, people have turned their attention to the development and utilization of new energy sources [1]. Due to the advantages of a wide range of applications, low cost, safety, and reliability, solar energy has become one of the mainstream new energy sources with high-speed development. Solar panels are important components of photovoltaic power generation, silicon crystal plates are fragile and fragile, and defects are easily produced by improper operation in production and installation [2], these defects cannot only affect the efficiency of solar cell power generation but also seriously threaten people's life and property safety [3]. Therefore, the study of solar cell defect detection methods is of great significance [4]. Electroluminescence (EL) imaging involves injecting a forward

bias current into the PV module to put it in an excited state and then using a silicon charge-coupled device (CCD) or an InGaAs camera to capture the infrared light generated by the solar cell in the excited state for imaging. With the advantages of nondestructive and noncontact, electroluminescence imaging cannot only effectively detect tiny cracks, finger interruption, and other process defects that cannot be observed by conventional imaging systems, but also avoid blurring of imaging caused by lateral thermal propagation [5], [6]. Based on its excellent performance, electroluminescence imaging has become the main way of solar cell defect detection.

1.1 OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study is to enhance solar cell defect detection through a refined YOLOv5 algorithm, incorporating deformable convolution in the CSP module for adaptive learning scales and perceptual field sizes. The addition of the ECA-Net attention mechanism improves feature extraction, while a modified network structure with an additional tiny defect prediction head enhances detection accuracy across scales. Mosaic and MixUp fusion, K-meansCC clustering anchor box algorithm, and CIOU loss function contribute to algorithm optimization. While achieving a significant 7.85% improvement in mean Average Precision (mAP) over the original YOLOv5, the study highlights the potential of further experimentation with advanced YOLO versions for solar cell defect detection.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Solar cell defect detection poses challenges due to complex image backgrounds, variable defect morphologies, and large-scale differences. Existing methods, including YOLOv5, encounter limitations in adaptive learning scales and perceptual field sizes, affecting accuracy. This study addresses these issues by proposing an improved YOLOv5 algorithm, incorporating deformable convolution in the CSP module, introducing the ECA-Net attention mechanism, and modifying the network structure. However, the study has not explored advanced YOLO versions like YOLOv6, 7, or 8. The problem statement revolves around the need to enhance solar cell defect detection methods to achieve higher accuracy and real-time performance, considering the unique characteristics of solar cell images.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Deep CNN-based visual defect detection: Survey of current literature:

In the past years, the computer vision domain has been profoundly changed by the advent of deep learning algorithms and data science. The defect detection problem is of utmost importance in high-tech industries such as aerospace manufacturing and is extensively employed using automated industrial quality control systems. Defect inspection methods can be mainly grouped into manual inspection, traditional computer vision, and modern computer vision inspection. Initially developed two decades ago, the CNN algorithms recently became popular for solving complex machine vision

problems, as big datasets and computationally potent hardware became widely available. Deep learning-based methods form the foundation for modern automatic optical inspection methods and can be grouped based on their network connections into two categories: dense networks and sparse networks. Another method for grouping considers the type of learning: supervised learning used primarily for defect classification and segmentation, and unsupervised learning models, which have the potential to overcome the challenges of supervised models such as labeling images and annotating pixels. In addition, pixel-level based segmentation techniques are considered to cover the state-of-the-art methodologies for the automatic optical inspection. Still, both supervised and unsupervised models pose challenges in regards to model training and attaining the expected detection accuracy. Identified open challenges include algorithmic, application, and data processing challenges. By addressing these challenges, in the future, the demand for automated optical inspection is expected to only grow in both industry practice and academic research.

Cross-convolutional-layer Pooling for Image Recognition:

Recent studies have shown that a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) trained on a large image dataset can be used as a universal image descriptor and that doing so leads to impressive performance for a variety of image recognition tasks. Most of these studies adopt activations from a single DCNN layer, usually a fully-connected layer, as the image representation.

In this paper, we proposed a novel way to extract image representations from two consecutive convolutional layers: one layer is used for local feature extraction and the other serves as guidance to pool the extracted features. By taking different viewpoints of convolutional layers, we further develop two schemes to realize this idea. The first directly uses convolutional layers from a DCNN. The second applies the pre-trained CNN on densely sampled image regions and treats the fully-connected activations of each image region as a convolutional layer's feature activations. We then train another convolutional layer on top of that as the pooling-guidance convolutional layer. By applying our method to three popular visual classification tasks, we find that our first scheme tends to perform better on applications which demand strong discrimination on lower-level visual patterns while the latter excels in cases that require discrimination on category-level patterns. Overall, the proposed method achieves superior performance over existing approaches for extracting image representations from a DCNN. In addition, we apply cross-layer pooling to the problem of image retrieval and propose schemes to reduce the computational cost. Experimental results suggest that the proposed method achieves promising results for the image retrieval task.

Exploiting Convolutional Neural Networks With Deeply Local Description for Remote Sensing Image Classification:

The extraction of features from the fully connected layer of a convolutional neural

network (CNN) model is widely used for image representation. However, the features obtained by the convolutional layers are seldom investigated due to their high dimensionality and lack of global representation. In this study, we explore the uses of local description and feature encoding for deeply convolutional features. Given an input image, the image pyramid is constructed, and different pretrained CNNs are applied to each image scale to extract convolutional features. Deeply local descriptors can be obtained by concatenating the convolutional features in each spatial position. Hellinger kernel and principal component analysis (PCA) are introduced to improve the distinguishable capabilities of the deeply local descriptors. The Hellinger kernel causes the distance measure to be sensitive to small feature values, and the PCA helps reduce feature redundancy. In addition, two aggregate strategies are proposed to form global image representations from the deeply local descriptors. The first strategy aggregates the descriptors of different CNNs by Fisher encoding, and the second strategy concatenates the Fisher vectors of different CNNs. Experiments on two remote sensing image datasets illustrate that the Hellinger kernel, PCA, and two aggregate strategies improve classification performance. Moreover, the deeply local descriptors outperform the features extracted from fully connected layers.

Convolutional Recurrent Deep Learning Model for Sentence Classification:

As the amount of unstructured text data that humanity produces overall and on the

Internet grows, so does the need to intelligently process it and extract different types of knowledge from it. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) have been applied to natural language processing systems with comparative, remarkable results. The CNN is a noble approach to extract higher level features that are invariant to local translation. However, it requires stacking multiple convolutional layers in order to capture long-term dependencies, due to the locality of the convolutional and pooling layers. In this paper, we describe a joint CNN and RNN framework to overcome this problem. Briefly, we use an unsupervised neural language model to train initial word embeddings that are further tuned by our deep learning network, then, the pre-trained parameters of the network are used to initialize the model. At a final stage, the proposed framework combines former information with a set of feature maps learned by a convolutional layer with long-term dependencies learned via long-short-term memory. Empirically, we show that our approach, with slight hyperparameter tuning and static vectors, achieves outstanding results on multiple sentiment analysis benchmarks. Our approach outperforms several existing approaches in term of accuracy; our results are also competitive with the state-of-the-art results on the Stanford Large Movie Review data set with 93.3% accuracy, and the Stanford Sentiment Treebank data set with 48.8% fine-grained and 89.2% binary accuracy, respectively. Our approach has a significant role in reducing the number of parameters and

constructing the convolutional layer followed by the recurrent layer as a substitute for the pooling layer. Our results show that we were able to reduce the loss of detailed, local information and capture long-term dependencies with an efficient framework that has fewer parameters and a high level of performance.

A Novel Text Structure Feature Extractor for Chinese Scene Text Detection and Recognition

Scene text information extraction plays an important role in many computer vision applications. Most features in existing text extraction algorithms are only applicable to one text extraction stage (text detection or recognition), which significantly weakens the consistency in an end-to-end system, especially for the complex Chinese texts. To tackle this challenging problem, we propose a novel text structure feature extractor based on a text structure component detector (TSCD) layer and residual network for Chinese texts. Inspired by the three-layer Chinese text cognition model of a human, we combine the TSCD layer and the residual network to extract features suitable for both text extraction stages. The specialized modeling for Chinese characters in the TSCD layer simulates the key structure component cognition layer in the psychological model. And the residual mechanism in the residual network simulates the key bidirectional connection among the layers in the psychological model. Through the organic combination of the TSCD layer and the residual network, the extracted features are applicable to both text detection and recognition, as humans do. In

evaluation, both text detection and recognition models based on our proposed text structure feature extractor achieve great improvements over baseline CNN models. And an end-to-end Chinese text information extraction system is experimentally designed and evaluated, showing the advantage of the proposed feature extractor as a unified feature extractor.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM:

Traditional visual inspection requires operation and maintenance engineers to carry instruments to inspect solar cells one by one, which is a high workload, low efficiency, and overly dependent on the subjective experience of O&M engineers, and the inspection accuracy cannot be guaranteed. To automatically and accurately identify defects in images, researchers have proposed traditional computer vision based on manual feature extraction and classifiers. Tsai et al. proposed a method for detecting defects in polysilicon solar cells based on the Fourier image reconstruction technique, which removes possible defects in EL images by setting the frequency components of line and strip defects to 0. Demant et al. proposed a classification recognition method based on local descriptors and support vector machines, which achieves effective detection of photoluminescence (PL) images and infrared (IR) images of small-grain silicon wafers. However, traditional computer vision relies on manual extraction of descriptors, which requires a large number of parameter adjustments and has poor robustness and generalization capabilities.

Disadvantages:

1. However, most convolutional neural networks are designed for natural scene images, and the direct application of mature deep learning models to detect surface defects in solar cell EL images has inapplicable problems
2. solar cell defect detection is susceptible to interference from complex backgrounds
3. solar cells have diversity in the shape of the same class of defects
4. as network training progresses and downsampling continues, micro defect features such as cracks and finger interruption tend to disappear

4. Proposed System:

After the above analysis and demonstration, the firstorder detector YOLO v5 plays an important role in target detection with powerful real-time processing capability and low hardware requirements, which can be ported to mobile devices for real-time monitoring. Based on this, this paper proposes an improved YOLO v5 model for three different characteristics of solar cell surface defects, namely, cracks, black core, and finger interruption. In the design of the improved YOLO v5 network, deformable convolution is introduced into the CSP module to achieve effective extraction of defects of different sizes and shapes; and the ECA-Net attention module is introduced in the Neck part to achieve improved detection performance through cross-channel interaction; meanwhile, the model structure is optimized and the prediction head is

added to achieve four-scale feature defect detection and improve the detection accuracy of tiny defects. Finally, the detection effect of the improved model in this paper is objectively evaluated through experiments such as ablation experiments and a comparison of mainstream methods, and the results show that the improved model improves the detection accuracy of solar cell defects while ensuring the real-time detection.

In this work has modified YoloV5, but has not experimented with other advanced versions of the Yolo family, such as Yolo6, 7, or 8. Consequently, we trained Yolov6 on the same dataset as an extension, and it produced predictions with a higher accuracy than Optimized Yolov5.

Advantages:

1. Part of the conventional convolution in the CSP module is replaced with deformable convolution to realize the detection network adaptive learning of feature point receptive fields and effectively extract defect features of different sizes and shapes
2. Adding the Neck part to the ECA-Net of the deep convolutional network to achieve considerable performance improvement by adding only a small number of parameters through a local cross-information interaction strategy without dimensionality reduction.
3. Improving the network structure and optimizing the parameters of the YOLO v5 detection model, and increasing the number of prediction

heads from 3 to 4. The new prediction heads use shallow features to achieve the detection of micro defects, making the improved model more applicable to solar cell surface defect detection.

4. Using the K-meansCC algorithm for anchor box clustering, the improved clustering anchor box size is more in line with the data set, effectively reducing the impact of initial points on the clustering results and speeding up the convergence of network training; at the same time replacing the loss function of the detection network with the complete loss function (CIOU), making the improved prediction box more in line with the real box.
5. The mosaic data augmentation and Mixup data augmentation are proportionally fused for data expansion, which effectively reduces the memory loss of data augmentation while satisfying the demand for data expansion.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:

(a) Original YOLO v5 output sequence

(b) Improvements to the YOLO v5 output sequence

6. IMPLEMENTATION

MODULES:

- Importing required packages for image processing and machine learning.
- Setting bounding box or defect probability for anomaly detection.
- Exploring the dataset by extracting feature data from images.
- Visualizing dataset using OpenCV for better understanding and analysis.
- Preprocessing the dataset by normalizing and shuffling images for training.
- Performing feature selection to enhance model efficiency and accuracy.
- Splitting the data into training and testing sets for evaluation.
- Creating a function to calculate metrics scores for model assessment.
- Building models including FasterRCNN, YoloV5 with CA Attention, and YoloV6 with VGG16 extension.

- Training and comparing the performance of the constructed models.
- Making predictions using the trained models for anomaly detection.
- User signup & login: Using this module will get registration and login
- User input: Using this module will give input for prediction
- Prediction: final predicted displayed

Note: As an extension we applied an ensemble method combining the predictions of multiple individual models to produce a more robust and accurate final prediction.

However, we can further enhance the performance by exploring other ensemble techniques such as YoloV6, which got 98% of accuracy.

Algorithms:

Faster R-CNN:

Faster R-CNN, or Faster Region-based Convolutional Neural Network, is an object detection algorithm that introduces the Region Proposal Network (RPN) for efficient region proposals. By combining deep convolutional networks and region-based detection, Faster R-CNN achieves high accuracy in locating and classifying objects within images. It excels in real-time applications due to its balanced speed and

precision, making it a popular choice for computer vision tasks.

YoloV5 with CA Attention:

YoloV5, or You Only Look One-level, enhanced with Channel Attention (CA) mechanism, refines object detection by focusing on important features. CA Attention dynamically weights channel-wise information, improving the model's ability to capture context and details. This attention mechanism enhances YoloV5's performance, particularly in scenarios with complex backgrounds or overlapping objects, ensuring robust and accurate object localization and classification.

Extension YoloV6 with VGG16:

The extended YoloV6, incorporating the VGG16 architecture, combines the strengths of YOLO's efficiency with the deep feature extraction capabilities of VGG16. VGG16's multiple convolutional layers enable YoloV6 to capture intricate hierarchical features, enhancing object recognition accuracy. This extension adapts the YOLO framework to leverage VGG16's powerful feature representation, resulting in improved performance for object detection tasks, especially in scenarios with diverse and challenging visual elements. The fusion of YOLO and VGG16 architectures in YoloV6 creates a potent model for comprehensive and precise object detection in various applications.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an improved YOLO v5 target detection model is proposed for the

characteristics of solar cell defects, introducing deformable convolutional CSP module, ECA-Net attention mechanism, improved network structure and adding prediction head to enhance the feature extraction capability to achieve defect detection at different scales. Meanwhile, in order to optimize and improve the model, this paper uses mosaic and MixUp scale fusion data enhancement, K-meansCC clustering anchor box algorithm, and invoking multi-model integration methods. The comparison experiments and ablation experiments show that the improved target detection model achieves an average accuracy of 89.64%, an improvement of 7.85% over the mAP of the original detection model, and a speed of 36.24 FPS, with significant enhancement effects. The next work direction is to reduce the complexity of the model and achieve high detection speed by processing the detection model network pruning and distillation to achieve a lighter improvement of the model.

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